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FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF EXTRACTED PEARL MILLET STARCH AS TABLET DISINTEGRANT IN DICLOFENAC SODIUM TABLET PREPARATION

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: This study aims to evaluate a novel tablet excipient obtained from local sources, Pearl millet *Pannistum americanum* starch of family Poaceae which is used locally as food because of its high carbohydrate content. It was thought that the starch of Pearl millet *Pannistum americanum* may serve as a tablet disintegrant. **Methods:** The excipient properties of Pearl millet starch as well as the pregelatinized form were studied in paracetamol tablets produced by wet and dry granulation methods of massing and screening and compared with maize starch BP. **Results:** Wet method showed superiority in all properties of both granules and tablets. Using wet method granulations Pearl millet *Pannistum americanum* starch and maize starch BP have similar angle of repose, Carr's index, tapped density, bulk density, and Hausner's ratio, however, Pearl millet *Pannistum americanum* starch has shown advantageous in some properties such as moisture content and swelling index. Tablet produced with Pearl millet *Pannistum americanum* starch disintegrated almost the same of those produced with maize starch BP at all concentrations employed. It was also found that when used as a disintegrant, the pre-gelatinized form provide tablets with better hardness and friability values than maize starch BP. **Conclusion:** This study confirmed the suitability of Pearl millet *Pannistum americanum* starch as an alternative to maize starch BP as a tablet disintegrant, particularly, in Diclofenac sodium tablet formulation.

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INTRODUCTION

Starch may be used to formulate tablets in which it acts as an excipient binder, diluent and disintegrant when incorporated in dry form mixed with the active ingredient prior to granulation (intragranular disintegrant) or may be mixed in dry form with lubricant/glidants prior to compaction of the granules into tablets (extragranular disintegrant) [1]. Disintegrants are substances incorporated into tablets to facilitate its breakup. After administration, the active ingredients in a tablet must be released from the tablet matrix as efficiently as possible to allow its rapid dissolution. Materials serving as disintegrants have been classified chemically as starches, clays, cellulose, sodium alginate, gums and cross-linked polymers that swell up in contact with moisture. The oldest and still the most popular disintegrants are corn and potato starch which have been used as dried form [1, 2].

The mode of disintegrant addition either internal or external normally has an effect on the breaking up pattern (intra-granular or extra-granular). Disintegration of the tablet matrix into granules is usually accomplished through one or more of the following processes: swelling of the tablet in a disintegrant. Aqueous environment as a result of water intake with subsequent bursting resulting in tablet breakup as hydration leads to the weakening of bonds in tablets.

Disintegrant efficiency depends on some factors such as: capacity for water uptake, disintegrant concentration, wettability of other components of the tablet, porosity of the system and size of disintegrant particles in relations to other tablets components [3].

For a drug to be fully available for absorption, the tablet must first disintegrate and discharge the drug to the body fluid for dissolution. Disintegration is also important for drugs acting locally in the GIT without absorption; it regulates their onset of action and availability. All tablets and capsules must pass a test for disintegration except chewable tablets, troches and modified or extended release tablets. Tablets meet the requirement if no fragments remain on the screen after the specified time in the monograph. The BP recommends a disintegration time of 15 min or less for uncoated tablets [4].

This study was carried out to investigate the disintegrant ability of Pearl millet *Pennisetum americanum* starch, in order to evaluate its disintegrant properties compared with maize starch MS BP in Diclofenac sodium tablets formulation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Pearl millet *Pennisetum americanum* grain was obtained from the market (Sebha, Libya). Diclofenac sodium BP was obtained from (Anqui Lu'an Pharmaceuticals, China), magnesium stearate was obtained from (SD Fine chemicals). Hydrochloric acid was obtained from (Fisher Scientific, U.K.), Iodine solution was obtained from (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany), Potassium hydroxide, Glycerin and Sodium hydroxide were obtained from (Carlo Erba Reagenti, Spain), Sulphuric acid 96% was obtained from (Park Scientific, Ltd., U.K.), Polyvinyl pyrrolidone, Potato, Lactose, Na-meta bisulphate and corn were obtained from (BDH "General purpose reagent" England).

Methods

EXTRACTION OF STARCH FROM PEARL MILLET PENNISTUM AMERICANUM GRAINS

The starches were isolated by a wet-milling method. Seeds were soaked for 24 hours at 4°C in 1% sodium metabisulfite, and after that altogether washed. Grains were blended with two volumes of refined water at 37°C and processed in a one-gallon warring mix for a few minutes at moo speed. The slurry was at that point screened on a 115-mesh screen. The build up was supplanted within the blender and homogenized with two volumes of water. The slurry was rescreened. The method was reshaped until the buildup showed up to be basically free of starch, which required 5-6 cycles. The suspension that passed through the screen was centrifuged in a strong bowl centrifuge, and the dull layer on best of the bowl was expelled with a spatula. The clear supernatant liquid was poured absent whereas sedimented starch was collected on a plate and air-dried. Utilizing pestle and mortar the dried starch knots were crushed and fine powder passed through 180 µm sifter. The starch was dried in broiler at 60°C.

Determination of Total Ash

Add up to cinder substance was decided as add up to inorganic matter by cremation of test at 55°C. Almost 2-4 g of the ground air-dried fabric, precisely weighed, in a already touched off and tarred cauldron (as a rule of platinum or silica). The fabric was spread in an indeed layer and lighted it continuously whereas expanding the warm to 450°C until it is white, demonstrating the nonattendance of carbon, at that point, cooled in desiccators and weighed. Fiery debris esteem was at that point calculated by utilizing the taking after equation:

$$\text{Ash value} = \left[\frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \right] \times 100$$

The percentage of water soluble and acid insoluble ash was calculated with reference to the air-dried starch.

Determination of moisture content

First, the container with lid were dried in the oven at 105°C for 3 hours then transferred to desiccator to cool. The empty dish and lid were weighed. About 5 g of the sample was weighed and spread uniformly. The dish with the sample were placed and dried in the oven for 3 hours at 105°C. Then the dish was transferred to the desiccator to cool. The dish and its dried sample were weighed.

Calculation: The % moisture content was calculated using the following formula:

$$\text{Moisture \%} = \left[\frac{W1 - W2}{W1} \right] \times 100$$

Where: W1: weight (gm) of sample before drying, W2: weight (gm) of sample after drying.

Determination of loss on drying

The starch was dried in an oven at 103°C by using halogen moisture analyzer, Halogen, (Mettler Toledo, USA) [5].

Determination of pH

The pH of 1 % w/v slurry was measured using a digital pH meter (Mathrom Ltd, Herison, Switzerland).

Determination of melting temperature and melting range

The melting range of a substance is the range between the corrected temperature at which the substance begins to collapse or form droplets on the wall of a capillary tube and the corrected temperature at which it is completely melted as shown by the disappearance of solid phase, the instrument used was BUCHI melting point B-540, Switzerland.

Determination of protein content

Crude protein was determined by the kjeldahl method. In present investigation kjeltic 2200 analyzer unit was used for determination of total crude protein according to total nitrogen amount and then multiplied by a factor of 6.25 to determine the total protein content.

OPTICAL ROTATION PRINCIPLE

The method comprises two determinations. Firstly, the sample is treated while hot with diluted hydrochloric acid 28 % v/v. After filtration, the optical rotation of the solution was measured using a polarimeter (Ap-100 Automatic Polarimeter at AGO, USA).

Secondly, the sample was extracted with 40 % ethanol (v/v). After acidifying the filtrate with hydrochloric acid, clarifying, and filtering. The optical rotation of the solution was measured by a polarimeter.

The difference between the two measurements, multiplied by a known factor that gives the starch content of the sample

SPECTROMETRY IN INFRARED REGION

The infrared region of the electromagnetic spectrum used in pharmaceutical analysis covers the range 250-4000 cm⁻¹ (2.5-40 μm). Spectrophometric measurements in the infrared region were used mainly as an identification tool. The instrument used was Fourier Transform infrared spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, Japan).

Sample preparation:

About 1 mg of the test sample was fine powdered; 200 mg of dried KBr fine powder were mixed well. The base sample was placed in the concave on the base (with shiny surface facing up).

MICROSCOPIC VIEW OF THE STARCH

One ml of glycerin and equal amount of water were mixed thoroughly and used as a diluent for the samples. Clean glass slide was taken and two drops of above prepared diluents were added. A loop full of sample was mixed with the diluents and covered with a cover slip. The structure of starch was viewed and the foreign particles were investigated in the samples [6].

Swelling index:

Prepared starch (100 mg) was added to 5 ml of each of water and light liquid paraffin taken in two different graduated test tubes and mixed. The dispersion in the tubes was allowed to stand for 12 hours. The volumes of the sediment in the tubes were recorded. The swelling index of the material was calculated as following formula:

$$S.I. \% = \left[\frac{VW - VL}{VL} \right] \times 100$$

Where: S.I. is the swelling index. VW is the volume of sediment in water. VL is the volume of sediment in liquid paraffin.

PHARMACEUTICAL EVALUATION OF STARCH**Angle of repose**

The determination of powder flow properties using angle of repose was done and then the evaluation of the influence of particle size on the powder flow ability was carried out.

Funnel method

The funnel was fixed on the stand then the distance between the lower edge of the funnel and the glass plate were adjusted to be 2 cm. The powder was allowed to flow through the funnel onto the glass plate beneath and formed a cone touching the lower edge of the funnel. The stand with the funnel was removed and the diameter of the circle formed at the bottom of the powder cone at two sides was determined. The average radius was estimated and the average was taken. The angle of repose was calculated using the following formula:

$$\tan \theta = h / r.$$

The same previously mentioned steps were repeated for three times and the average was taken. The angle of repose for other size fraction was calculated as well.

PARTICLE SIZE ANALYSIS

Particle size analysis by sieving method:

The particle size reduction was performed using hammer mill. A stack of sieves consisting of (1000, 710, 350, 250 & 180 mm) sieves were used (Sieves Shaker RETSCH, Germany). The sieves were weighed and their weights were recorded. The sieves were arranged from smallest to the largest. A sample of 20 g was placed on the coarsest sieve at the top of the stack.

The stack was placed on the mechanical shaker for a period of 10 min each sieve was weighed with the material retained. The weight of each fraction was determined. The mean particle (d_s) diameter was calculated using the following formula:

$$(d_s) = \sqrt{\frac{\sum \varepsilon d^2 x}{\sum \varepsilon x}}$$

The data obtained were analyzed and presented using over size and histogram.

Electron microscopy

Electron microscopy has been useful in the morphological study of starch granules. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) exhibits good depth of field and gives detailed information about the surface of dry granules.

GRANULATION AND GRANULE EVALUATION

In order to perform granulation and to evaluate the granules obtained.

Preparation of granules

Wet granulation:

The sample (s) and excipients (lactose + p.v.p) were mixed. The binder solution and powder mixture were mixed to form wet mass. Then, the wet mass was subjected to granulation by using oscillating granulator. The wet granules were weighed, before and after drying. Finally, the dry granules were screened through a suitable sieve (250-100 μ m).

Dry granulation:

The weighed test sample was placed on the top sieve of the chosen nest. Then shaken for a pre-determined period. The sieving continued to an "end point". After which, the sieves were individually removed from the nest and shaken vigorously by hand. Any sieve load that failed this test was returned to the nest for further sieving.

Evaluation of granules

Friability of granules:

The granule friability was determined in a friabilator, (TA-20, Erweka, Germany). The drum was rotated at a speed of 25 rpm for 10 min, by subjecting 10 g (Iwt) of granules (F250-1000 μ m) together with 200 glass beads (mean diameter 4 mm) to falling shocks. Afterwards the glass beads were removed and the weight of the granules retained on a 250 μ m sieve (Fwt) was determined after vibrating for 5 min. The friability was calculated as follows:

$$\% F = \left[\frac{Iwt - Fwt}{Iwt} \right] \times 100$$

Bulk and tapped density:

The bulk volume (V_o) of 50 g (weight that overfills 100 ml measuring cylinder) granules (F250-1000 μ m) were recorded in a 100 ml measuring cylinder as well as the volume after x taps (V_x). Bulk and tapped densities were calculated as 50 g/ V_o and 50 g/ V_x , respectively.

Compressibility index and Hausner Ratio:

The bulk and tapped densities were used to calculate the Carr's compressibility index "CI" and the Hausner ratio "HR" to provide a measure of the flow properties.

$$CI = \frac{P_{tap} - P_{bulk}}{P_{tap}} \times 100$$

Where P_{tap} : are the density and the bulk density.

PREPARATION OF TABLETS

Direct compression weight of 402 mg of granules were compressed using hand operated I.R press with a flat face 15 KN punch and set Hydraulic press, (Shimadzu, Japan). The ejection time was 1.9 seconds.

Preparation of Diclofenac sodium granules

Working formula for the assessment of Pearl millet starch as disintegrant in Diclofenac sodium tablets is given in **Table 1**. The wet granulation method of massing and screening was used in preparing all batches of Diclofenac sodium granules. The Diclofenac sodium powder and the intradisintegrant maize starch or Pearl millet starch of concentration between 3 to 12 % w/w depending on the batch were dry-mixed for 5 min in a Zblade mixer (Bibby Sterilin Ltd., UK). An appropriate quantity of freshly prepared starch mucilage of concentration 6 % W/V was added to each of the batch to produce granules. The wet mass was passed through a 1.8 mm 1800 μ m sieve mesh screen, then wet granules were dried at 47°C to constant weight in a Memmert hot air oven (GmbH & Co. KG, Germany) and then later dried screened through sieve mesh 1-1.5 mm (150-100 μ m).

Evaluation of starch powder and Diclofenac sodium granules

Table 1: Formula used in the preparation of the Diclofenac sodium granules and tablets.

Ingredients	Quantity /tablet(mg)
Diclofenac sodium	50
Disintegrant*	
Binder mucilage (7.5 % w/v maize starch)	q.s
Magnesium stearate (0.2 % w/w)	1.30
Talc (2.0 % w/w)	13.00

*The disintegrant, P. americanum starch or maize starch BP (3, 6, 9, and 12 % w/w)

The Diclofenac sodium powder and PA and MS starches (intra disintegrant) were weighed appropriately and dry mixed for 5min in a mortar with pestle until fine powder was obtained. An appropriate quantity of freshly prepared binder of concentration of 7.5% w/v was added depending on the batch to produce a moist and cohesive mass. The wet mass was then passed through a 1.7mm sieve mesh screen and then oven dried at 40 °C for 30min after which they were re- screened through a 1.6mm mesh size and further dried for another 30min. The granules were allowed to cool and stored in an air tight container.

Particle size analysis:

The particle size distribution of the starches and the granules were determined by sieve analysis, using series of sieves of different sizes. The weight percentage oversize as a function of size was studied.

Friability of starch powder and Diclofenac sodium granules

The starch powder or granule friability was determined in a friabilator at a speed of 25 rpm for 5 min, by subjecting 10 g (Iwt) (F250-1000 µm) of starch powder and Diclofenac sodium granules with 200 glass beads (mean diameter 4 mm) to falling shocks. Afterwards the glass beads were removed and the weight of the granules retained on a 250µm sieve (Fwt) was determined after vibrating for 5 min. The friability was calculated as:

$$\% F = \left[\frac{Iwt - Fwt}{Iwt} \right] \times 100$$

Bulk and tapped density of starch powder and Diclofenac sodium granules

The bulk density of the starches (Pearl millet starch and maize starch BP as a standard for comparison) and the granules samples were determined using a graduated measure. Fifty grams of each granules and starches powder were gently and slowly poured into the measuring cylinder. The volume occupied by the granules was read to the nearest 0.5 ml and the bulk density was calculated. The tapped density of the various size fractions of the starches and the Diclofenac sodium granules was measured. A weighted quantity of each fraction was placed in a graduated measuring cylinder and tapped 50 times on a hard table surface, after which the volume was noted.

Starch powder and Diclofenac sodium granules flow properties

Methods described in the USP were used for the determination of angle of repose, Hausner's ratio and Carr's compressibility index [7].

QUALITY CONTROL TESTS

Official tests described by the BP and USP include weight and content uniformity (uniformity of dosage unit), disintegration, dissolution and friability tests.

Non compendial tests

Tablet diameter, thickness and hardness (Crushing strength):

Diameter, thickness and hardness of tablets were determined by using hardness tester instrument (PHARMATEST PTB 311, Germany), measuring the average force in Kilogram by triplicate of tests as well as measuring in mm for thickness and diameter.

Compendial tests

Uniformity of weight:

Twenty tablets from each batch were randomly selected and weighed together; the tablets were then weighed individually. The weight of each tablet was subtracted from the mean tablet weight and the percentage deviation of each tablet from the mean was calculated as described in BP, 2014.

Friability:

Erweka tablet friabilator (Erweka, Milford CT, Germany) was used to determine the friability of Levar tablets according to the method described in the BP.

Disintegration study:

Disintegration studies were performed according to USP specifications using the disintegration test apparatus (Tablet Disintegration Tester, ZT-4, Erweka, and Milford, Germany). Six tablets from each brand were placed in basket rack assembly of apparatus. Basket was moved with frequency of 29 to 32 cycles per minute in distilled water, maintained at $37 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$.

Dissolution Rate

The dissolution rates of the active drug from tablets were determined using BP specification equipment (Erweka dissolution Apparatus, Model DT 600, Germany). The dissolution medium was (900ml) of phosphate buffer with pH 5.8 at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and rotate the paddle at 50 rpm. The samples were withdrawn at specified time intervals. Filter and dilute to reach the solution expected to contain about 0.00075% w/v of Diclofenac, then spectrophotometrically analyzed at 257 nm using 0.1 M sodium hydroxide in the reference cell. Samples removed for analysis were replaced with fresh aliquots of dissolution medium. The total content of Diclofenac sodium, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2$, was calculated in the dissolution rates of the active drug from tablets were determined using BP specification equipment (Erweka dissolution Apparatus, Model DT 600, Germany). The dissolution medium was (900 ml) of phosphate buffer with pH 5.8 at $37^\circ\text{C} \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and rotate the paddle at 50 rpm. The samples were withdrawn at specified time intervals. Filter and dilute to reach the solution expected to contain about 0.00075 % w/v of Diclofenac sodium, then spectrophotometrically analyzed at 257 nm using 0.1 M sodium hydroxide in the reference cell. Samples removed for analysis were replaced with fresh aliquots of dissolution medium. The total content of Diclofenac sodium, $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{NO}_2$, was calculated in the medium taking 715 as the value of A (1%, 1cm) at the maximum at 257 nm. All experiments were conducted in triplicates, and the average readings were recorded.

RESULTS

Organoleptic properties of the fresh Pearl millet starch and commercial maize are illustrated in Tables 1. The presence of starch in the samples used was confirmed by Molish's test and Iodine test.

Table 1: Organoleptic properties of fresh Pearl millet and maize starch BP.

Test	Pearl millet	Maize Starch BP
Color	White	White
Odor	No characteristic	No characteristic
Taste	Taste less	Taste less
State	Fine-powder	Fine-powder
Inference	Powder complied with the BP and USP organoleptic test for starch	

The physicochemical parameters of the Pearl millet compared with maize starch BP are shown in Table 2. The pH of the Pearl millet starch (4.06) was more acidic compared to commercial maize starch pH (5.0). Table 2 also shows the proximate composition which is a major determinant of starch purity. It also determines the presence of all other contaminants or impurities other than pure starch. The ash content of the Pearl millet starch was higher than that of commercial maize starch by 0.000176 % w/w.

Table 2: Physicochemical parameters of the Pearl millet and maize starch BP.

Physicochemical Parameters	Pearl millet Starch	Maize Starch BP
Total ash	0.00026818%	0.0000923%
Water soluble ash	0.000051178%	0.00005047%
Acid insoluble	0.00006249%	0.00009128%
Sulphoric acid ash	0.000677%	0.000116%
Moisture content	18.897%	10.5045%
Loss on drying	17.62%	10.1%
pH	4.06	5.00
Melting point	289-290 °C	299-300 °C
Protein	5.737%	1.475%
Lipid	0.919	0
Fiber	0.0%	0.0%
Optical rotation	73.043%	70.923%
I.R.	96%	88%
Swelling index	58.33%	50%
Content CHO	74.44%	88.025%

The physico-chemical characteristic properties of granules of Diclofenac sodium produced with Pearl millet starch and maize starch are listed in Table 3. The angle of repose provides an insight into the extent of the cohesiveness and hence flowability of the granules.

The results of granule size distribution as containing Pearl millet starch disintegrant were illustrated in Figure 1 using dry and wet granulation methods, indicating the suitability of the wet granulation method using Pearl millet starch as a disintegrant.

Table 3: The physico-chemical characteristic properties of Diclofenac sodium granules.

The physico-chemical characteristics	Pearl millet	Maize Starch BP
Water soluble cold	Insoluble turbid white colour	Insoluble turbid white colour
Water soluble hot	Insoluble Ppt	Insoluble turbid white colour
Ethanol cold	Ppt	Sparingly soluble white colour
Ethanol hot	Insoluble	Sparingly soluble white colour
Petroleum ether cold	Insoluble Ppt white colour	Insoluble
Ether cold	Insoluble Ppt	Insoluble
Hot ether	Insoluble Ppt	Insoluble
Molish's test	+ ve	+ ve
Iodine test	+ ve	+ ve
Shape	polyhedral	Polyhedral
Size	4.kx-2.85kx	4.kx-2.00kx
Angle of repose	38.12(\pm 1.20)	37.67(\pm 1.85)
Hausner's ratio	1.24(\pm 0.18)	1.23(\pm 0.10)
Carr's index	19.5%(\pm 0.21)	19.04%(\pm 0.32)

Figure 1: Particle size of maize starch BP at magnifications 4.00 KX (A) and particle size of Pearl millet starch at magnifications 4.00 KX (B).**Table 4: Results of varying disintegrant type/concentration on Diclofenac sodium tablet properties produced by wet granulation method.**

Tablet properties	Disintegrant type /concentrations (% w/v)							
	Pearl millet				Maize starch			
	3 %	6 %	9 %	12 %	3 %	6 %	9 %	12 %
Weight variation %w/w	-0.98 to 1.379	0.2 to 0.907	0.2 to 0.4	-0.98 to 0.907	-0.51 to 0.4	-0.98 to 0.4	-0.98 to 1.40	-1.1 to 3.74
Friability %w/w	0.56	0.53	0.49	0.32	0.59	0.53	0.37	0.29
Hardness (Kg F)	11.42	13.20	13.41	14.73	10.76	12.3	13.01	14.03
Tablet thickness (mm)	5.4	5.3	5.25	5.15	5.6	5.5	5.31	5.25
Disintegration* time (min)	10.37	6.07	5.57	3.07	15.68	5.45	4.5	3.5
Dissolution time T50 (min)	31.12	15.37	13.34	5.06	26.07	14.25	12.01	6
Dissolution time T90 (min)	59	30.44	23.23	11.58	40.5	28.76	21.2	10.45

*Disintegration times were not more than 15 min (BP, 2013).

The disintegration time of Diclofenac sodium tablets containing the Pearl millet starches as disintegrant was not marginally faster than compacts containing the commercial maize starch (Table 4). In addition, similar pattern of variation was observed with dissolution time of the tablets, as the concentration of disintegrant has had impact in increasing dissolution time.

Figure 2: Normal distribution curve for wet method of Diclofenac sodium with Pearl millet starch showing the Mean diameter of particles = 530µm.

Figure 3: (A) Shows the IR spectra for Pearl millet starch, and (B) Shows IR spectra for maize starch.

DISCUSSION

Starch amylose is reported to form a characteristic dark blue color complex with iodine. This colour complex observed in the investigations confirmed the identity of materials obtained from the wet separation process as starch. The percentage yield of starch extracted from Pearl millet (*Pennisetum americanum*) crop was 65.6% w/w which was a very good yield and high dry matter content 82.38%, tend to have firm texture as tuber water content is relatively low [8], and can enhance water binding capacity and adhesive or binder property of the starch. It may however reduce flow properties as it causes adhesion to substrates. The Pearl millet starch granules as well as that of the commercial maize starch were either round, irregularly round or polyhedral in shape. Starch granule size and size distribution contribute to the temperature and rate of gelatinization. There are reports of less molecular bonding with faster swelling in larger starch granules, such starch granules would therefore be of interest to the pharmaceutical manufacturing industry, as their high swelling capacity will hinder them stronger tablet disintegrants [9, 10]. The physical and chemical properties showed differences in bulk and flow properties as well as acidity and hygroscopicity of Pearl millet starch. The high indices of powder flow ability observed, confirmed reports of native starches generally having poor flow properties [11]. Both Pearl millet starch and commercial maize starch had high angle of repose and very similar Hausner's ratio and Carr's index values. They would therefore be ideal for wet granulations, where improved granule flow (as a result of the increased powder density) allows smooth tablet compression [12, 13]. The pH of the Pearl millet starch was more acidic compared to commercial maize starch that was with pH value of 5.

The starches should therefore be used with caution in formulations of low dose alkaline drugs to prevent drug-excipients interaction. On the other hand, effectiveness of other excipients such as the parabens, which act as antimicrobial preservatives may however be enhanced as they are more active in acidic conditions [14,15]. The BP recommends a pH range of 4.0-7.0 for starch [4].

The spectra for Pearl millet starch and Mize starch did not show any significant change in position of the absorption bands. The ash content indicates amount of insoluble salts and complexes in starch. Presence of inorganic salts and ions of phosphorous, sodium, iodine and hydroxyl groups in starch have been reported to contribute significantly to starch granule swelling and gelatinization [16].

Using dry and wet granulation methods indicated the suitability of the wet granulation methods in using Pearl millet as a disintegrant. The angle of repose provides an insight into the extent of the cohesiveness and hence flow ability of the granules. It was observed as the concentration of the disintegrant increased the crushing strength of the tablets increased. Pearl millet starch gave harder tablet than maize starch when used as disintegrant.

The differences in tablet hardness and friability among compacts prepared using the Pearl millet starch as disintegrant were however not significant. The tensile strength and mechanical integrity of tablets are known to improve significantly when low density regions or voids are eliminated [17]. Void elimination has been demonstrated to reduce incidences of tablet capping and lamination; and may be achieved if the material has either high binding capacity or the compression load or quantity of binder is increased [18].

Conventional compressed tablets of acceptable hardness (4-6 kg/cm²) and friability (\leq 1%) are essential for handling during packaging, transportation and administration [19].

The disintegration time of Diclofenac sodium tablets containing the Pearl millet starches as disintegrant showed significant differences compared to that of compacts containing the commercial maize starch. Starch granules as extra-granular disintegrant undergo deformation during high pressure tablet compression; and these swell maximally in aqueous fluids to cause tablet disintegration. Its disintegration time decreased with increase in disintegrant concentration and friability values as well were found to decrease with an increase in disintegrant concentrations.

The BP, 2007 recommends a disintegration time of 15min or less for immediate release tablets, the mechanisms of action of starch as a disintegrant in tablets are still not clear but some important postulates were proposed by Pate and Hopponen [20] and Nogami et al, [21]. The mode of action of starch as a disintegrant is that water penetrates into the tablet porous structure causing the starch grains to swell and exert pressure on the granules to break them a part. The disintegration time decreased as the concentration of the disintegrant in the formulation was increased. Others proposed that starch does not swell when exposed to water but that the disintegrating force of starch is due to capillary action rather than swelling. This capillary action tends to bring aqueous fluids to the tablet, where they may exert hydrostatic pressure, dissolve the binding agents and cause swelling of some components, so that all or any of these actions may serve to break the tablet apart.

The pattern of in-vitro dissolution and drug release closely followed that of tablet disintegration. Tablets which disintegrated quickly released Diclofenac sodium faster than tablets which took a longer time to disintegrate.

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